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- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

Цифровизация социально-трудовых отношений: вызовы и перспективы для работников.....	18
Абдумухтаров Анваржон Акрамжонович	
O'zbekistonda faoliyat ko'rsatayotgan soliq to'lovchi yuridik shaxslarning iqtisodiy faoliyatini rag'batlantirish masalalari.....	26
To'xtaboyev Nuriddin Isomiddin o'g'li	
Ecotourism in Protected Areas: A Literature Review.....	32
Ismoilova Maftuna Mamat qizi	
Iqtisodiyotning innovatsion rivojlanishi sharoitida xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirishning hududiy xususiyatlari.....	38
Primova Shaxlo Jumayevna	
Statistik baholash va ekonometrik modellashtirish orqali biznes rivojlanish tendensiyalarini samaradorligini baholash.....	43
Xabibullayev Ibrohim, Saidova Marhabo Xabibullo qizi	
Tijorat banklarida xususiy kapital hisobi va auditini takomillashtirish.....	52
Qodirova Zilola Maxmud qizi	
Qo'shilgan qiymat solig'i ma'muriyatchiligining ilg'or xorij tajribasi.....	57
Erkayev Nodir Xudayberdiyevich	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotni joriy etish holati va asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	71
Madraximova Zulfiya Nurmatovna, Ishankulova Komila Kurbanovna, Ortiqboeva Aziza Xolmurza qizi, Omonkulova Ro'zigul Akmaljon qizi	
Challenges and opportunities in implementing green economy indicators in uzbekistan's industrial sector under the fourth industrial revolution.....	76
Shodmonov Ruslan Golib ugli, Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarga ishchi kuchi oqimi va O'zbekiston mehnat bozoridagi o'zgarishlar.....	89
Tilabova Kumush Farhod qizi	
Mamlakatda "yashil" iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish.....	95
Yuldashboyev Azizulloh Bunyodbek o'g'li, Matkarimov Inomjon Baxtiyorovich	
"Ta'lim muassasalarida moliyaviy resurslarni samarali rejalashtirish va boshqarish".....	101
Bauyetdinov M.J., Medetbayeva D.T.	
Enhancing utilization and minimization of renewable energy systems in uzbekistan.....	105
Toyrova Hamida Umedovna	
Tijorat banklari daromadini oshirishda aholining savodxonligi va xulq atvorining roli.....	114
Shakhlo Davirova	
2020–2024-yillarda o'zbekistondagi iqtisodiy o'sish dinamikasi.....	120
Akbarov Nodir, Ibodullayev Navro'zbek	
O'zbekistonda xalqaro moliyaviy institutlarning yashil moliyalashtirish jarayonidagi roli va strategik yo'nalishlari.....	125
Gulmira Axmadjonova Xabibulla qizi	
Sug'urta tizimiga raqamli texnologiyalarning ta'siri.....	133
Uzaqova Kamola Bexzodovna, Yahyoyev Bahriddinxon Bahroil o'g'li	
Improving payment services practices in commercial banks: strategies for efficiency and security.....	138
Mamayusuf Abdusamatov	
Jahon moliya tizimi: asosiy tendensiyalar va rivojlanishning innovasion yo'nalishlari.....	143
Ataniyazov Jasurbek Xamidovich	
Повышение конкурентоспособности экологического туризма Узбекистана путём развития всесезонных горных туристических центров.....	150
Ахмедходжаев Равшан Темурович	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyatida valyuta operatsiyalarini takomillashtirish.....	157
Safarov Alisher Ibrohim o'g'li	

Oliy ta'lim tizimini miqdoriy va sifat ko'rsatkichlari asosida baholashning kompleks metodologiyasi.....	163
Hakimova Mushtariybonu Hamid qizi, Bozorova Muazzam Hamid qizi	
Ko'chmas mulkni boshqarish samaradorligini baholashning uslubiy yondashuvlari	167
Mirdjalilova Dildora Shuxratovna	
Xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirishda kichik biznesning ahamiyati va uning innovatsion rivojlantirishdagi muhim xususiyatlari	173
Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna	
Результаты долгосрочного прогнозирования и стратегического анализа эффективной организации современного управления жилищным фондом.....	178
Бердиева Дилфуза Ахатовна	
Improving long-term assets accounting and auditing	184
Gulboy Yusupov	
Davlat budjeti va xususiy sektor ishtirokida oliy ta'limni moliyalashtirishning optimal modeli.....	189
Bozorov Alisher Ro'zimurodovich	
Xufyona iqtisodiyotni qisqartirishda soliq islohotlari va raqamli texnologiyalar: O'zbekiston tajribasi va xalqaro yondashuvlar.....	193
Choriev Makhmayokub, Karimov Mamurbek, Xamrayev Olimjon, Urazov Mansur	
Bank aksiyalarining bozordagi narx dinamikasi va unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	200
Nomozov Samandar Shuxrat o'g'li	
Sanoatda rivojlanish kafolati: moliyaviy boshqaruvni raqamli transformatsiya orqali avtomatlashtirish.....	206
To'qliyev Abdirauf Bahodir o'g'li	
Inson kapitalini rivojlantirishning jamiyat farovonligi, aholi daromadlariga ta'siri.....	214
Bozorova Saxobat Abdujapparovna	
Анализ конкурентной среды: методология, примеры и этапы процесса.....	219
Садикова Раъно Абдуллаевна	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarning nazariy asoslari va ular bilan ishlash mexanizmining zaruriyati	225
Salixova G.J	
Iqtisodiyotda energiya xavfsizligiga erishishning xorij tajribasi.....	230
Samandarov Og'abek Alisher o'g'li	
Measuring methodologies of influence of the esg factors	235
Tolipova Feruza Alisherovna	
Совершенствование налогового администрирования в условиях экологически устойчивого развития.....	240
Омонов Отажон Журакулович	
Moliyaviy vositalar asosida erkin iqtisodiy zonalarni rivojlantirish strategiyasini takomillashtirish	249
Quziev Ravshan Ramazanovich	
Методологические аспекты внедрения управленческого учета в университетах Узбекистана.....	253
Каршиева Мохинур Олим кизи	
Budjet tashkilotlarida tovar-moddiy zaxiralar hisobini takomillashtirish (tibbiyot muassasalari misolida)	257
Tulyaganov Abdumalik Abdiraximovich	
Умные города как фактор экономического развития.....	261
Нозима Кахрамоновна Хакбердиева	
Перспективы зеленого фактора экономического роста в Республики Узбекистан.....	266
Исламова Насиба Улугбек кизи, Абдурашидов Отабек Улугбекович, Мамасалиева Мукаддас Ибадуллаевна	
Qurilish korxonalarida sifat menejmentini joriy qilish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	270
Ergashev O'tkir, Saidov Mash'al Samadovich	
Xorazm viloyatida eksportni rivojlantirish uchun potensial imkoniyatlar va ularni baholash.....	275
Fozil Xolmurotov	
Maishiy xizmatlar sohasini davlat tomonidan tartibga solishning nazariy jihatlarini.....	282
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	

O'zbekiston hududlarida chakana kreditlashning o'sishi.....	289
Eshqobulova Charos O'roq qizi	
Empowering uzbekistan's grain enterprises: innovative strategies for sustainable growth and operational efficiency.....	292
Kurbanova Dildora Abdurakhmanovna	
Kapital investitsiyalarga doir axborotlarni xususiy kapital to'g'risidagi hisobotda aks ettirish uslubiyatini takomillashtirish	298
Boronov Bobur Farxodovich, Muxammadiev Zarrux Umarovich	
To'qimachilik korxonalarining yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishi va yengil sanoat korxonalarini muqobil energiyadan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	303
Xolbekova Feruzaxon Rasulovna, Jalolova Aziza Jalol qizi	
Research on the effects of interest rate, inflation rate and gross domestic product (GDP) on the level of foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows (evidence from Uzbekistan).....	307
Azimov Shakhzod	
Organik mahsulotlar eksportini rag'batlantirishda maqsadli bozorlarga yo'naltirilgan marketing strategiyalari.....	314
Xidirov Shohrux Bobir o'g'li	
Korxonada iqtisodini barqarorligini ta'minlash masalalari.....	319
Abdullayev Maqsud Abdumaxmudovich	
Внедрение инновационных методов управления человеческих ресурсов в строительных компаниях.....	323
Джуроева Гузаль Шавкатовна	
Sug'urta zararlarini baholashda sun'iy intellektni qo'llash istiqbollari	328
Shoraximova Zilola Nasirdjonovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi mahalliy budjet tizimini moliyalashtirish masalalari	332
Qo'ldoshev Diyov O'rol o'g'li	
Raqamli texnologiyalar asosida raqamli ekotizimlar va ularning biznes-jarayonlarga ta'sirini aniqlashga ilmiy qarashlar tahlili	336
Suvanova Dilnoza Dilmurod qizi	
Innovatsion salohiyatni oshirish asosida qurilish materiallari sanoati korxonalarining boshqaruv mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	342
Xaydarova E'zoza Shukurullayevna	
Aholi turmush darajasini dinamik kontekstli normallashtirish va moslashuvchan vaznlar usuli orqali baholash	352
Xolto'rayev Islom Ilhomovich, Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xufiyona iqtisodiyotini qisqartirish va mamlakat rivojlanishiga uning ta'siri.....	358
Baxtiyov Sherali Muzaffarovich	
Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalari qurilmalarini aholi tomonidan xarid qilish va kompensatsiya ajratish jarayonlarini raqamlashtirish hamda tizimlar integratsiyasi istiqbollari.....	362
Ochilov Abdujabbor Akramovich	
O'zbekistonda kambag'allikni qisqartirish va aholi farovonligini oshirishda chet el tajribasining afzalliklari.....	369
Raxmatullayeva Shaxnoza Xamidovna, Akbarova Iroda Samatovna	
Qurilishda loyiha boshqaruvi konsepsiyasining mazmuni	375
Pulatov Shaxron Axmedovich	
Loyiha budjeti va uning ijrosini ta'minlash masalalari.....	379
Murodova Mohigul Chori qizi, Xamidov Odil Davurovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligidagi chorvachilik tarmog'ining iqtisodiy faoliyatini o'rta muddatli statistik prognozlarini tuzish (Andijon viloyati misolida).....	390
Iskandarov Davlatbek Xursanbekovich, Urishev Baxtiyor Abdusamatovich, Muydinov Xusniddin Nuriddin o'g'li	
Innovatsion faoliyatning iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash va rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	397
Qurbanov Tolmasjon Namoz o'g'li, Shodiyev Fazliddin Qalandar o'g'li, Holmirzayeva Gulruh Akbarovna	
Fond bozorida kompaniyaning investitsion jozibadorligini baholash uslubi.....	403
Yulduz Usmanova	
Jahon bozoriga kirishda elektron bozorlarning ahamiyati.....	411
Hamroyeva Umida	

Comparative statistical analysis of foreign trade indicators of the Republic of Uzbekistan	415
Abdujalilova Bibisora Bakhodir kizi	
Yaxshi korporativ boshqaruv orqali aktsiyadorlik jamiyatlarining kapital qiymatini oshirish: metodologik yondashuv.....	423
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
JAS – barqaror qishloq xo‘jaligini rivojlantirishning yapon modeli vositasi	423
Baynazarov Elmurod Erkinovich	
Xususiy banklarning depozit operatsiyalarini mustahkamlash yo‘llari	435
Olimov Abror Axadjon o‘g‘li	
The impact of digital financial technologies on the financial system.....	439
Yahyoyev Bahriddinxon Bahroil o‘g‘li, Pardayev Olim Mamayunosovich	
Korxonalar eksport salohiyatini oshirishning “yashil” marketing mexanizmi	443
To‘rayev Shohrux Halimovich	
O‘zbekistonda ichki turizmni rivojlantirishda turistik oqim mavsumiyligini boshqarish yo‘llari	448
Fayazov Muxiddin Sobirovich	
Sanoat korxonalarida qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalaridan foydalanish bo‘yicha xalqaro tendensiyalar	453
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Ayollar tadbirkorligining tarixi: O‘zbekiston va dunyo bo‘yicha rivojlanishi.....	459
Burxonova Sabo Tulanovna	
Qimmatli qog‘ozlar bozorida investorlar risklarini pasaytirishni takomillashtirish yo‘llari.....	466
Xalilov Umid Ishtemirovich	
Korxonalar moliyaviy ko‘rsatkichlari tahliliga fundamental yondashuv.....	470
Dilshodjon O‘rinov, Sanobar Ismoilova	
Iqtisodiy o‘zgarishlar davrida korxonalar moliyaviy barqarorligining ta‘minlanishi omil va mezonlari	475
Xolbekova Dilobarxon Rasuljon qizi	
Cash accounting as a tool of financial discipline and transparency in the public sector.....	481
Marqaboyev Sardorbek Abdusalomovich, Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich	
Пути совершенствования практике финансирования социального предпринимательства.....	486
И.Ж.Исаков	
O‘zbekistonda an‘anaviy resurslar va qayta ishlanadigan energiya manbalarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlaridan unumli foydalanish.....	490
Normurodov Xusan Eshmaxmatovich, Kaxramanova Sevda Shamsiddin qizi	
Ijtimoiy salohiyat – hududiy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning boshqaruv obyekti sifatida.....	497
Erkayeva Gulbahor Panjiyevna, Zoirov G‘olibjon Toshtemir o‘g‘li	
Xorazm oziq-ovqat bozorida mahsulotlarning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda marketing faoliyatlarini baholash usullari	503
Abdikarimova Zilola Bahramovna	
Переход к зелёной энергетике узбекистана как возможность достижения устойчивого экономического роста.....	508
Бай Жин Хуан (Bai Jin xuan)	
Изучение условий финансирования проектов международными банками развития	513
Жалилова Барнохон Суръатжоновна	
O‘zbekiston respublikasi budjet jarayonida budjetlarning ochiqligi va jamoatchilik ishtirokini oshirish.....	517
Shodmonqulov Temurbek Ulug‘bek o‘g‘li	
Chiqib ketayotgan aktivlarni hisobga olish va baholash masalalari	522
Kuziyeva Dinora Bahodirovna	
Asosiy kapitalga investitsiyalarning iqtisodiy o‘lishga ta‘siri.....	528
Qo‘shbaqov Aybek Shovqiyevich	
Changes in employee benefits and human resource management in accounting system of the Republic of Uzbekistan	535
Ravshanbekov Lazzbek Tolibjon o‘g‘li, Toshpulatova Munisabonu	

Iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarida suv iste'molini boshqaruvining raqamlashtirish tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish istiqbollari.....	541
Karimov Anvarjon Muqumjonovich	
Теоретические аспекты налогообложения доходов физических лиц на основе всеобщего декларирования	547
Усманова Мухлиса Сагдуллаевна	
Bank tizimini raqamlashtirish va uning bank barqarorligiga ta'siri.....	555
Sayfullayev Jamshidjon Xabibjanovich	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirish va aholi bandligini ta'minlashda tadbirkorlik faoliyatining o'rni.....	560
Saparov Ismat Chorshanbiyevich	
Innovatsion korxonalarda xarajatlar hisobining zamonaviy usullari	565
Turayev Og'abek Kaxramonovich, Ochilov Shavkat Toshmamatovich	
Дополнительные услуги в индустрии гостеприимства как эффективный инструмент продвижения бренда предприятия.....	570
А.И. Лесников, Д.В. Мамаева	
Преимущества и вызовы перехода на зелёную экономику.....	580
Умарова Гузал Гайратовна, Лапасова Камола Фарход кизи	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida hududlarda ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish	586
Ibrogimov Sherzodbek Xalimjon o'g'li, Djurayeva Maxliyoxon Xayrullayevna	
Yashil iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashda bevosita soliqlar rolini oshirish masalalari.....	591
Abdullayev Dilmurod Aliyar o'g'li	
The main directions for improving innovative activities in agriculture	598
Aytmuratova Miyrigul Zhalgasovna	
Klaster tizimi orqali O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligining iqtisodiy o'sishi	605
Xaydarov Sardor Komil o'g'li	
Inklyuziv ta'lim: adolatli va teng jamiyat sari.....	610
Muxamedjanova Dilshodxon Muzaffarovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot: muammo va yechimlar	615
Boymatov Xoliyor Qurbonovich	
Issues of using foreign loans in the development of the transport system in the Republic of Uzbekistan	621
Alimov Ilhomjon Ikromovich	
Проблемы и резервы развития пищевой промышленности в экспортном направлении.....	628
Ўролова Севара Бехзод кизи	
Оценка степени риска инновационной деятельности.....	634
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна	
Yashil innovatsiyalar, ularning turlari va omillari.....	638
Maxkamova Sayyora Shokirovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida transport tizimidan samarali foydalanishning nazariy asoslari.....	641
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
Soliq ma'murchiligida nazorat funksiyasi va unda kameral soliq tekshiruvi hamda takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	648
Hujamuradov Abrorbek Ro'zimurat o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalarida xarajatlarni mahsulot tannarxiga taqsimlash metodologiyasini takomillashtirish istiqbollari	653
Safarov Javohir Ismoilovich	
Moliyaviy hisobotlarni shakllantirishda milliy standartlarni xalqaro standartlarga uyg'unlashtirish masalalari	659
G'aniyev Zafar Usanovich	
Ta'lim kreditini moliyalashtirish jamg'armasi faoliyati.....	666
Adilov Zuxriddin Marip o'g'li	
Tibbiyot muassasalarining moliyaviy ta'minoti va resurslardan foydalanish mexanizmlariga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar	670
Elmurodov G'ayratjon Abdumurodovich	
Tourism finance for sustainability: investing in green futures	674
Tashpulatov Sadriddin Sayfulloevich	

Ta'lim jarayonlarini boshqarishda mobil texnologiyalar	681
Esonova Mohiraxon Sodiqjon qizi, Ovхunov Iqboljon Abdunabiyevich, Sherzodbek Nabiyev Nurmuhammad o'g'li	
Banklarda risklarni nazorat qilishning amaliyoti	686
Jumanazarov Muzaffar Jumanazar o'g'li	
Налоговые реформы в Узбекистане: вызовы, достижения и перспективы	692
Садиков Искандар Гайратович, Буранова Лола Вахобовна	
Turizm xizmatlari samaradorligini baholash usullari va vositalari tahlili	704
Jiyanov Uktam Panjiyevich	
Korxonalar va tashkilotlarda xodimlarni boshqarish strategiyasi	712
Raxmonova Feruza Musakulovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti direktorlarini menejerlik faoliyatiga tayyorlashning ahamiyati	716
Dusmaxamedov Abduljalil Abdusabirovich	
Davlat korxonasini xo'jalik jamiyatiga o'zgartirishning foydali jihatlari	720
Z.D. Sanjarov	
The role and main types of agricultural tourism in Uzbekistan	724
M.Xolmuratova, G.N.Tojiyeva	
Цифровые технологии как драйвер повышения эффективности банковского маркетинга	727
Кахрамонов Хуршидjon Шухрат угли, Маннабова Хулкар Фарход кизи	
Потребительская стоимость товаров в условиях экономики Узбекистана	735
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна	
Valyuta risklarini boshqarishda metching siyosatining ahamiyatini oshirish	739
Yaxuyayev Ziyodilla Lutfullayevich	
Yangi o'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida xususiy tadbirkorlikning roli va ahamiyati	744
Azimova Shoxista Salohiddinovna	
Improving the methodology for assessing the financial stability of banks	750
Sharipova N.H.	
Инструменты стратегического планирования и прогнозирования в управлении ООО "МТЕ ТЕХНИК": оценка и повышение финансовой стабильности	757
Нишоновна Муниса Одилжон кизи	
Актуальные вопросы налоговой политики	763
Бердыева Угулой Абдурахмоновна	
Ilm-fanni moliyalashtirish va innovatsiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash jamg'armasi	768
Ramazonov Javohir Bekzod o'g'li	
Jizzax viloyatida ekologik, rekreatsiya turizmlarini rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash va uni prognozlashtirish	773
G'apparov Azim Qayumovich	
Qashqadaryo viloyatida ekologik va yashil texnologiyalarga kiritilayotgan investitsiyalar	781
Meylikov Fazliddin Abduhalim o'g'li, Buriyev Shaxbos Baxtiyorovich	
Biznes subyektlari auditida soddalashtirilgan moliyaviy hisobot tayyorlash usulini qo'llash xususiyatlari	786
Tajekeev Ziyatdin Kobeyisovich	
Biznes jarayonlarni modellashtirishning nazariy asoslari	791
Mullajonova (Matchanova) Shaxsanam Taxirovna	
Raqamli xizmatlar bozori: elektron tijorat orqali xizmat ko'rsatishning yangi bosqichlari	796
Maxammadaliyeva Muslimaxon Sherali Qizi	
"Yashil iqtisodiyot"ga o'tish zaruriyati va uni barqarorlashtirishning ahamiyati	800
Musurmankulova Gulchehra Isabekovna	
Ekologik turizm nuqtai nazaridan turizm marketingining usullari va asosiy vositalarining xususiyatlari	806
Yokubjonova Xulkarbonu Yokubovna	
O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida turizmning o'rni va rivojlanish istiqbollari	815
Qosimova Fazilat, Kalandarov Ravshan	
Korporativ strategiyani ishlab chiqish bosqichlarining tahlili	819
Xidirova Marg'uba Rustamovna, Abduvasiyeva Marjona Anvarovna	

Mamlakatimiz turizmini rivojlantirishda investitsiyalarni jalb qilish bo'yicha o'tkazilayotgan islohotlarning o'rni.....	823
Ayubov Ilyos Ilxomovich, Nuridinov Bexruz Akbar o'g'li	
Hududlarda tadbirkorlarning islomiy investitsiyalardan foydalanish niyatlariga undovchi omillarning empirik tadqiqoti.....	829
Irgasheva Gulbahor	
Davlat vositalari yordamida innovatsion faoliyatni moliyaviy rag'batlantirish yo'nalishlari	836
Baxriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
Важность качества управления на предприятиях общественного питания.....	842
Абдуллаева Зульфия Иззатовна, Махмудов Суннатжон Абдужаббор Угли	
O'zbekistonda "yashil" moliyalashtirishni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	848
Shaislamova Nargiza Qabilovna	
Mahalliy budjetning qo'shimcha daromadlarini shakillantirish yo'nalishlari.....	856
Yuldashev Javohirbek Ikromjon o'g'li	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishni kengaytirish masalalari.....	860
Ro'zimatova Nigora Abdullaevna	
Принципы «справедливой стоимости» в мсфо: достоинства и проблемы применения в банках узбекистана	869
Айтмуродова Рушана Бахтиеровна	
Yashil iqtisodiyot loyihalarini moliyalashtirishning nazariy jihatlari	876
Allaberganova Asalxon Kadirovna	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratini tashkil etish hamda amalga oshirish tartibini takomillashtirish	880
Xasanov Ruslan Rahmatovich	
Yirik soliq to'lovchilar va ularning investisiyaviy faolligini investisiyaviy chegirmalar orqali rag'batlantirish	883
Tohirov Shuhrat Niyoz o'g'li	
MHXS bo'yicha moliyaviy hisobot tayyorlashda foydalaniladigan tuzatuvchi buxgalteriya yozuvlar.....	888
Sheraliyev Xayrulla Karimovich	
Qurilish korxonalarida investitsiyalarni boshqarishning xorijiy tajribalari va ularni mamlakatimizda foydalanish yo'llari	894
Karimov Inomjon Ortikbaevich	
Davlat xaridini tashkil etishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy amaliyati va uni iqtisodiyotga ta'siri.....	900
Burxanov G'ofur Baxodirovich	
Влияние технологических инноваций на международные финансовые рынки, а также на финансовый рынок нашего государства.....	904
Бабаназарова Гульзар Зиуатдиновна	
Strategic development of global companies in modern conditions.....	909
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Hududlarda sog'liqni saqlash tizimi asosiy ko'rsatkichlarini noaniq modellashtirish yordamida kompleks baholash.....	914
Ismoilova Dilfuza Ibodullayevna	
Tijorat banklari faoliyatini transformatsiyalashuv jarayonlarini takomillashtirish.....	923
Kulboyeva Nargiz Majitovna	
Сущность и причины возникновения проблемных кредитов.....	929
Улмасой Ахмедова Хусан кизи	
The use of digitalization and technologies in updating credit policy.....	934
Otabek Ma'mirjon ogli Azimov	
Финансовое моделирование сценариев развития предприятия с использованием методов многокритериального принятия решений (МКПР).....	938
Axmedov Akbarali Sultonmurodovich, Yuldosheva Gulnoza Abdinabievna	
Yuqori samarali energiya tejash texnologiyalari va katalizga asoslangan konversiya jarayonlari.....	945
Yusupov Ulug'bek Mamayusupovich	
Kambag'allikni kamaytirish maqsadida aholining ijtimoiy himoyalash mexanizmini takomillashtirish	951
Kasimova Gulyar Axmatovna	

Tijorat banklarida foiz riski muammosi	957
Turdiyev Abdulhakim Kulbazarovich	
Milliy mahsulotlarni tashqi bozorlarga olib chiqishdagi to'siqlarni bartaraf qilish choralari.....	964
Abdivaliyev Shahzodbek Xayrullayevich	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni moliyalashtirish usullari.....	970
Kaxorova Zamira Safaraliyevna	
O'zbekistonda mehmonxonalarda ovqatlantirish xizmatlarini takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi: strategik yondashuv.....	974
Yaxshiyev Xusniddin Tolibovich	
O'zbekiston sanoatida "yashil texnologiyalar" dan foydalanish va barqaror rivojlanish.....	979
Ubaydullaeva Gulchehra Erkabaevna	
Sanoat korxonalarida resurslarini rejalashtirish (ERP) tizimlarini joriy etishning orqali iqtisodiy samaradorlikni ta'minlash yo'llari.....	985
Azizov Abdulla Abdisalamovich	
Yashil texnologiyalar asosida sanoatni modernizatsiya qilish	990
Muftaydinov Mansur Kiyomidinovich	
Ta'lim va ilm-fan rivoji – taraqqiyot garovi	995
Jamalova Gulnora Gulomovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida turizm sektorida barqaror bandlikni ta'minlash masalalari.....	1000
To'rabekov Sohijon Sherboy o'g'li	
Yashil energitikasi integratsiya qilish va energiya samaradorligini oshirishning zamonaviy usuli (aqli tarmoqlar-smart grids)	1007
Karimova Salima Elamonovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida soliqlarni raqamlashtirishni takomillashtirish	1012
Jo'rayev Botir Abdiyevich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotda tiklanadigan energiya manbalaridan foydalanish samaradorligi (TEM ko'rsatkichlar izohi)	1018
Sharifova Nargiza Djurayevna	
Экономическое образование молодёжи основа будущего страны.....	1023
Айматова Фарид, Айтиниязова Наргиза	
Biznes turizmining bugungi kundagi rivojlanish tendensiyasi.....	1028
Yangiyeva Sabrina Ixtiyorovna, Daniyarova Feruza Bahriddinovna	
Особенности кредитования сельскохозяйственных организаций и этапы его развития.....	1032
Ж.Я.Нуриллаев	
Xorijiy tajriba asosida O'zbekiston yashil iqtisodiyotini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	1039
Xikmatova Husnora Fatxulla qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda davlatning roli	1045
Umarov Muzaffar Yusupbayevich, Otamurodov Rasulbek Batirovich, Xaitbayev Jasurbek Otaxanovich, Atadjanov Kadambay Sapayevich	
Mintaqada raqamli transformatsiya rivojlanishida moliyaviy texnologiyalarning ahamiyati.....	1052
Rustamov Jasurbek Ravshanbek o'g'li	
Tijorat banklaridan olingan kreditni qaytarishda foiz stavkalari ta'sirining tahlili.....	1058
Xanmuratov Roushenbek Xalmuxammetovich, Vaxabov.A.V	
Tabiiy va sun'iy tolalarning ekologik ta'siri va yashil ishlab chiqarish texnologiyalariga o'tish bosqichlari.....	1066
Raximov Furqat Jalalovich	
Maishiy kimyo tovarlari B2B taqsimotida chakana savdo tarmoqlari bilan marketing asosidagi strategik hamkorlik	1071
Ro'ziyeva Farzona Komiljon qizi	
Мировой финансовый кризис и его влияния на состояние экономики Узбекистана	1076
Раупова Мхлисахон Ибрахимжон кизи	
Uzoq muddatli aktivlar hisobini xalqaro standartlar asosida takomillashtirish.....	1087
Hakimov Faxritdin Abdusattorovich	
O'zbekistonda tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	1093
Djo'rayeva Lola Abdugabbarovna	

Yo'l qurilish tashkilotlarida yo'l qurilish ko'lamini oshirib, samarali resurslar taqsimotini ishlab chiqish.....	1099
Raximov Dilshodjon Turdiali o'g'li	
Ilg'or xorij tajribalaridan O'zbekiston amaliyotida foydalanish imkoniyatlari	1104
Karimova Komila Daniyarovna	
Ichki audit samaradorligini tahlil qilish metodologiyasi.....	1111
I.G'.Isroilov	
Выведение практического сотрудничества на качественно новый уровень государств центрально-азиатского региона в укреплении концепции «зеленой экономики» в эпоху глобализации.....	1117
Парпиева Наргиза Тахировна	
Kimyo sanoati korxonalarida lean production konsepsiyasidan foydalanish istiqbollari	1122
Gulbayeva Feruza Islomovna	
Qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida auditorlik xizmatlarining ahamiyati.....	1127
Maxmudov Saidjamol Kadirjanovich	
Tijorat banklari resurs bazasini mustahkamlash yo'llari.....	1131
Allaberganov Sirojali Saxatovich	
Теоретические основы формирования понятия «финансовая стабильность» Часть II.....	1143
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
O'zbekiston moliya tizimini raqamlashtirishning rivojlanish tendensiyalari.....	1148
Tashmatova Rano Gaibovna, Qodirov Nurhayot Normuhammad o'g'li	
Theoretical basis of the use of modern information technologies in accounting.....	1154
Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich, Tojiboyev Jasurbek Shavkat o'g'li, Rustamov Suxrob Asror o'g'li	
Moliyaviy bozorlar chayqalmoqda: investorlar uchun yangi signalmi?	1158
Xushvaqov Islombek Muxammadi o'g'li, Yaxshiboyev Jahongir Abdualimovich	
Yashil moliyalashtirish va esg samaradorligining iqtisodiyot barqarorligidagi o'rni.....	1166
Yusupov Sherzodbek Baxtiyor o'g'li, Atadjanov Kadambay Sapayevich, Madraimov Xabibulla Madaminovich	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarni kamaytirish bo'yicha tizimlarni takomillashtirish yo'llari	1170
Bekmurodova Mahbuba Mahmudovna	
Maqola: Globalizatsiyada inson resurslarini boshqarishda raqamli transformatsiyaning rejasini tuzish	1177
Salimjonova Gulhayo Asliddin qizi, Ovxunov Iqboljon Abdunabiyevich, Nabiye Sherzodbek Nurmuhammad o'g'li	
Turizm sanoatida Internet-marketing vositalari va ulardan samarali foydalanish	1182
Babaev Jo'rabek	
Ishlab chiqarishni boshqarishda mahsulot tannarxini kalkulyatsiya qilishning ahamiyati.....	1190
Asqarova Lobarxon Usmanjanovna	
O'zbekistonda ichki turizm faoliyatini rivojlantirishda transport infratuzilmasini boshqarishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy jihatlarini	1194
Turovov Maqsudjon	
Kichik biznes faoliyatini rivojlantirishda soliq siyosatini takomillashtirishning ahamiyati	1199
Abdurahmonov Abdumalik Abdug'ani o'g'li	
Madaniy-tomosha xizmatlarining tahlili va uni rivojlantirish yo'llari	1204
Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich	
Цифровизация экономики и генезис стран мирового хозяйства	1211
Камилова Наргиза Абдукажоровна	
“Oila va xotin-qizlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash jamg'armasi” faoliyati.....	1216
Xushmurodov Baxtiyor Turg'un o'g'li	
Soliq stavkalarini tabaqalashtirish asosida soliq to'lovchilar iqtisodiy faoliyatini tartibga solish mexanizmlari.....	1220
Abduraimova Nigora Abdugapparovna	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish va barqaror rivojlanishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	1223
Xamdamov Shoh-Jahon Rahmat o'g'li	
Mintaqaning eksport salohiyati tahlili asosida istiqbolli y'nalishlarni aniqlash (Xorazm viloyati misolida).....	1229
Ibadullayev Ergash Bakturdiyevich	

Uy-joy kommunal xo'jaligini mintaqada innovatsion rivojlantirishni boshqaruvi.....	1235
Adilova Yulduz Shavkatovna	
Bank tizimi likvidligini ta'minlash vositalari va usullarini takomillashtirish	1239
Poyonov Bobir Bekmurod o'g'li	
Milliy brendlarni shakllantirish orqali tashqi bozorlarda raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish	1245
Muratbaeva Eleonora Muxamedjan qizi	
Charm mahsulotlaridan tayyorlangan bolalar transformatsion sumka ishlab chiqarish iqtisodiy samaradorligi	1250
Ismailov Nurulla Tuychibayevich	
O'zbekistonda qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalar faoliyati: iqtisodiy tahlil va islohotlar zarurati	1256
Raximov Ilyos Ikramovich	
Yoqilg'i-energetika kompleksida innovatsion salohiyatni oshirish strategiyasi.....	1262
Nabiyeva Saidaxon Abduvaxabovna	
Banklarda moliyaviy xavfsizlik kategoriyasining evolyusiyasi.....	1268
Qobilov Muhammad Ayubxon Yusufjon o'g'li	
Развитие системы бухгалтерского учёта и отчётности на современном этапе	1273
Мамажонов Акрамжон Тургунович, Юсупова Малика Ботиралиевна	
Практика банковского кредитования предпринимательских субъектов сферы услуг в германии	1279
Мукарова Сарвиноз Маликовна, Каримова Азиза Махомадризовна	
Статистический анализ теневой экономики в узбекистане	1283
Кошанов Абдимурат Азат ули, Абдиразакова Асемай Жандулла кизи	
The importance of using digital technologies in business	1288
Makhmudova Munisakhon Abbos qizi	
0,4 kv kuchlanishdan ta'minlanuvchi suv nasoslarini tarmoq faza kuchlanishi yo'qolishidan himoyalash.....	1292
Xalikova Xurshida Abdullayevna, Nurova Malika Abduzairovna, Mustayev Ruslan Aktamovich	
Tijorat banklarida korporativ boshqaruv tizimining samaradorligini oshirish	1297
Dexkonova Sayidaxon Nurmuxammatovna	
Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiyot va markaziy osiyo mamlakatlari ijtimoiy sohada	1302
Usmanxo'jayeva Surayyo Muxtarovna	
Aksiyalarni ommaviy joylashtirish amaliyotini tashkil etish va o'tkazish bosqichlari	1307
Raimov Farrux Avazjon o'g'li	
Approaches to effective management of tax liabilities through tax auditing	1311
Abdullayev Abror Bozarboevich	

APPROACHES TO EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF TAX LIABILITIES THROUGH TAX AUDITING

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Abstract: The article explores the strategic role of tax auditing in the effective management of tax liabilities within enterprises under the current phase of economic liberalization and modernization in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It discusses the theoretical foundations and practical significance of tax audits in aligning corporate tax practices with the evolving fiscal legislation. The study emphasizes the importance of improving tax discipline and strengthening tax control through audit mechanisms. Modern challenges such as digitalization, international compliance, and the need for administrative transparency are also addressed. The methodological approach includes a comparative analysis of domestic tax audit practices with international standards. Results suggest that tax audits not only enhance tax compliance but also serve as a preventive tool against violations. The paper concludes with policy recommendations aimed at optimizing state tax administration and integrating global audit frameworks.

Key words: enterprise, tax liability, taxation, tax audit, tax control, fiscal discipline, tax administration, audit standards, international compliance, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida iqtisodiyotning erkinlashuvi va modernizatsiyasi sharoitida korxonalarining soliq majburiyatlarini samarali boshqarishda soliq auditing strategik roli o'rganiladi. Soliq auditing nazariyasi asoslari va amaliy ahamiyati yoritilib, mavjud fiskal qonunchilik bilan korxonalar soliq amaliyotini uyg'unlashtirish zarurati asoslanadi. Soliq intizomini kuchaytirish, soliq nazoratining sifatini oshirish va bu jarayonda audit mexanizmlarining tutgan o'rni tahlil etiladi. Shu bilan birga, raqamlashtirish, xalqaro standartlarga muvofiqlik va soliq boshqaruvida shaffoflikni ta'minlash kabi dolzarb muammolar ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot metodologiyasi sifatida ichki va xalqaro audit amaliyotlarining qiyosiy tahlili tanlangan. Natijalar audit tekshiruvlari soliq tartib-intizomini oshiruvchi va buzilishlarning oldini oluvchi vosita ekanligini tasdiqlaydi. Xulosa qismida davlat soliq boshqaruvini takomillashtirish va xalqaro standartlarga integratsiyalash bo'yicha takliflar ilgari suriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: korxonalar, soliq majburiyati, soliqqa tortish, soliq auditi, soliq nazorati, fiskal intizom, soliq ma'muriyatchiligi, audit standartlari, xalqaro muvofiqlik, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается стратегическое значение налогового аудита в эффективном управлении налоговыми обязательствами предприятий в условиях текущего этапа либерализации и модернизации экономики Республики Узбекистан. Раскрываются теоретические основы и практическая значимость налоговых проверок для приведения налоговой практики предприятий в соответствие с изменяющимся фискальным законодательством. Отдельное внимание уделено укреплению налоговой дисциплины и повышению эффективности налогового контроля посредством аудита. Также анализируются современные вызовы, включая цифровизацию, международную совместимость и необходимость административной прозрачности. Методологически применён сравнительный анализ отечественной и международной практики налогового аудита. Результаты исследования показывают, что налоговый аудит способствует не только повышению уровня соблюдения налоговых требований, но и служит механизмом профилактики нарушений. В завершении статьи представлены рекомендации по совершенствованию налогового администрирования и интеграции международных аудиторских стандартов.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, налоговое обязательство, налогообложение, налоговый аудит, налоговый контроль, фискальная дисциплина, налоговое администрирование, аудиторские стандарты, международная совместимость, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, ensuring the free activity of business entities and fair competition, significantly reducing state interference in their operations, enhancing the effectiveness of preventive measures to ensure compliance with tax legislation, and creating a favorable investment climate are considered crucial priorities for economic development.

These aspects highlight the necessity for an in-depth study of enterprise tax liability systems and measures for effective management of their tax capabilities to assess the initial outcomes of the tax system modernization that began in 2018. Within the framework of the new tax policy concept developed in the context of economic modernization and liberalization and considering the country's future socio-economic development tasks, there is a need to intensify research in this field. This is due to the growing importance of systematically studying the impact of taxes on enterprises' financial and economic activities and creating an improved mechanism by coordinating and harmonizing the following aspects:

- establishing an electronic accounting system based on the digital economy;
- paving the way for entrepreneurial activities based on free competition;
- balancing state fiscal goals with effective mechanisms of tax leverage, which is a crucial foundation for financial support of socio-economic development.

The *Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026* outlines measures to improve the regulation of tax and customs benefit provision. This aims to ensure competition in the economy, create equal conditions for business entities, accelerate the full transition to market relations, increase the competitiveness of the national economy, dramatically expand private investments, and further strengthen the confidence of business circles [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

At the micro-level, tax planning manifests itself in the form of a financial plan for enterprises, i.e., taxpayers, to fulfill their imposed tax obligations. Most economist-scholars mistakenly interpret the essence of tax forecasting and tax planning processes as synonymous categories.

Some economists [2] interpret the process of tax planning in enterprises as an integral part of financial planning aimed at minimizing tax expenses and maximizing the financial results of the enterprise within the framework of tax legislation. Here, tax minimization refers to the full utilization of existing benefits through a thorough analysis of changes in current legislation, as well as reducing costs by avoiding excessive fines through the timely fulfillment of tax obligations. Therefore, cost minimization in the tax planning process is distinct from concepts and practices such as tax evasion, tax avoidance, or paying less than the actual amount of taxes due.

In some literature [3], the process of tax planning is interpreted as the budgeting process in enterprises, while some economists view tax budgeting as a comparative analysis of income saved through proper tax planning and the costs associated with the tax planning process. Additionally, the aforementioned literature outlines methods of implementation within the enterprise, including: formulating the enterprise's tax policy, analyzing the economic and legal activities of the enterprise, modifying economic relationships, allocating relationships, deferring tax payments, directly reducing taxable objects, and similar approaches.

However, without entirely dismissing the importance of approaches related to the organizational stages of the tax planning process in enterprises, we would like to present our own scientific approach to its organization and implementation. We will explain this through the "Special Model of Tax Obligation Management in Enterprises" proposed below.

The essence of this model is that it reflects the complex results of processes related to tax obligations in the enterprise in their sequential order. In our opinion, one of the following objectives can be taken as a basis: determining the enterprise's ability to pay taxes and mandatory payments; analyzing the relationship between the enterprise's tax obligations and monetary funds; assessing the factors influencing the fulfillment of the enterprise's tax obligations; or developing ways to minimize the enterprise's tax and mandatory payments.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed general scientific methods and techniques to reveal the interpretation of human capital for management accounting purposes and its classification. In particular, methods such as analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, monographic observation, and grouping were used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the main challenges in taxation theory is determining the optimal tax burden for taxpayers. Economic agents, who are interested in maximizing profits through the rational use of enterprises' financial resources, tend to reduce their tax burden as much as possible within the framework of their tax obligations. There are primarily two approaches to this: reducing tax liabilities through structural efficiency in economic activity, and decreasing the tax burden by shifting it to other economic agents. These issues were initially addressed in the

scientific works of economists A. Marshall, P. Samuelson, and A. Pigou.

In the 1970s–1980s, American economist A. Laffer established the relationship between tax revenue and tax rates. The effectiveness of this relationship was demonstrated by the fact that tax revenues increase when the tax rate is up to 50%, but decline when the rate exceeds 50%. Among scholars, this relationship is known as the Laffer curve [4].

As is known, in addition to regulating economic processes through taxes, the state also acquires the financial resources necessary for fulfilling its functions. The introduction of taxes, the preparation of state budget parameters through tax forecasting, increasing the level of tax collection, and improving tax administration form the basis of the state's policy in this area. Moreover, the implementation of corporate tax management is ensured through the selection of taxation procedures by corporate structures, adaptation to available benefits and preferences, and assessment of the tax implications of contracts [5].

The Tax Code and other subordinate legal documents do not define the content of the concept “*tax factors for effective management of enterprise financial resources*,” nor do they specify the procedure for organizing and improving the tax budget at the enterprise level.

Table 1. Analytical overview of tax burden management and audit prospects in Uzbekistan

Key Aspect	Current Situation	Prospects for Uzbekistan
Tax Burden Optimization	Enterprises seek to reduce burden within legal limits	Develop legal instruments for lawful tax minimization
Laffer Curve (Tax Rate vs. Revenue)	Relationship proven; revenue drops after 50% threshold	Use Laffer curve for optimal rate calibration
State Role in Tax Policy	Used for budget planning and economic regulation	Modernize fiscal planning through smart tools
Legal Gaps in Tax Budgeting	No clear definition or framework in legislation	Define and regulate enterprise-level tax budgeting
Positive Tax Regulation	Focus on minimizing tax side effects	Enhance tax incentives and equity measures
Tax Discipline and Compliance	Need for higher voluntary compliance	Adopt improved tax discipline frameworks
Multilevel Tax Compliance Approach	Exists: International, National, Enterprise levels	Formalize multilevel compliance strategies
Enterprise Tax Accounting Objectives	Lacks standardization in all enterprises	Standardize internal tax policy frameworks
Tax Audit Functions	Checks accuracy of reporting and payments	Increase use of external tax audits
Risk Prevention via Tax Audit	Helps avoid penalties and optimize tax planning	Embed audits in preventive risk strategies

One of the important methods to positively influence the formation of financial foundations for socio-economic development is to enhance the positive impact of taxes while reducing their negative effects. This is considered a crucial task in regulating enterprise activities through taxation. Any enterprise has the right to use effective methods and approaches within the framework of the law for conducting business and recording economic operations, in order to minimize its tax obligations to the state budget (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Model of tax liability formation¹

A noteworthy aspect of Figure 1 is that, although the existence of an enterprise's tax duty operates objectively within the framework of current legislation, it does not yet allow for assessing the full scope of tax liability and the possibilities for its fulfillment.

It is necessary to improve the principles of taxation in accordance with the new requirements of tax practice, which include methods for enhancing tax discipline and increasing the share of voluntarily paid taxes by taxpayers. This is because ensuring a balance of mutual interests among participants in the hierarchy of tax relations depends on the principles of the tax system that influence taxpayer behavior. Such a balance is achieved by adhering to both basic and supplementary principles that account for the role of the state in the economy, the characteristics of modern tax bases, and the transaction costs of taxation.

To substantiate a new approach for strengthening corporate tax discipline aimed at increasing voluntary tax payments, the application of improved tax discipline principles in corporate tax planning allows for enhanced effectiveness in forecasting tax revenues, stricter adherence to tax obligations by taxpayers, and improved tax collection rates [6].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a systematic approach to the scientific study of corporate tax compliance within the context of corporate financial management and the modernization of the tax administration system requires its examination as a multilevel relationship structure:

International level – considering global standards for corporate tax compliance systems, international financial reporting standards (IFRS), and international tax agreements;

National level – organizing tax compliance accounting and analysis based on domestic standards, industry-specific characteristics, and current tax legislation requirements;

Enterprise level – developing a strategy and tactics for the company's internal tax accounting policy.

Timely and accurate payment of taxes and mandatory contributions by legal entities primarily depends on the quality of their tax accounting, which is a critical component of tax management. Proper organization and maintenance of tax accounting involve clearly defining its main objectives, including:

¹ Developed by the author based on the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

- Timely and accurate calculation of taxes and mandatory payments by legal entities;
- Ensuring prompt payment of accrued taxes and contributions to the state budget and designated state funds;

- Maximizing the use of legally established tax benefits and exemptions.

Tax audit refers to the verification of the accuracy, timeliness, and completeness of tax calculations in accordance with the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the proper preparation and submission of all forms of tax reporting to tax authorities. Verification of tax obligations may be conducted through a formal tax audit or via agreed procedures for validating the correctness of tax calculations. The primary significance of tax audits lies in their role in the timely assessment and minimization of tax risks faced by enterprises.

A tax audit involves the examination of accounting and tax reports by an auditing firm to form an expert opinion regarding their reliability and compliance with current tax legislation. It also includes verification of procedures related to the formation, payment, and accounting of taxes and other payments to budgets and off-budgetary funds at all levels.

Drawing upon existing scientific literature on tax auditing, a tax audit can be defined as a comprehensive, independent review of an enterprise's tax records, focusing on the accuracy of tax calculations and payments, and the identification of tax-related risks within business activities.

Ultimately, a tax audit is a service that offers a detailed evaluation of the audited enterprise's tax reporting. It aims to identify inaccuracies in accounting or financial statements, or to eliminate discrepancies that contradict the tax legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main goal of a tax audit is to prevent penalties for violations of tax laws. During the audit process, the auditing organization seeks to resolve all issues related to tax optimization and planning in the best interest of the client.

Conclusion and Suggestions

In general, the result-oriented incentive system aimed at enhancing the role of tax audits in planning and effective management of an enterprise's tax obligations includes the following:

New requirements for modernizing the enterprise's tax liability fulfillment system – These entail adapting the system to international standards and developing national standards in accordance with the requirements of a market economy.

Enterprise tax management is a system of measures aimed at calculating, paying, analyzing, preparing, and submitting reports on tax obligations, considering their legal and regulatory framework, as well as tax payments. It also includes taking into account the system of tax benefits and incentives, and effectively managing these processes.

An enterprise's accounting policy is a set of legally binding documents that reflect the application of generally accepted regulatory documents, principles, and methods in organizing accounting by an economic entity in accordance with its specific characteristics [7].

A key strategic direction has been defined as the transformation of the state tax service into a service-oriented agency. This involves creating a new institutional image as a business partner and advisor to taxpayers, where each employee is expected to fulfill the target task: *"Tax Service – a reliable partner of conscientious taxpayers."*

Through tax audits, an assessment of the reliability of the audited accounting object is established. In the process of examining an enterprise's tax liabilities, it is necessary to widely and effectively use analytical procedures, as these help focus the auditor's attention on problem areas. This improves audit quality by identifying risks during the planning phase and determining key indicators, such as the materiality level.

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